

SELF TEST AND IMPROVED SELF REPAIR FOR AI ACCELERATOR THROUGH RECURSIVE APPROACH

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Abstract

Many AI accelerators have been proposed as a result of the rapid advancement in artificial intelligence (AI) and the resulting growth in demand for data-intensive analytics. However, the dependability of AI-based solutions has become a crucial concern as they have been tailored to applications that demand precision and consistency. Self-testing and self-recovery for artificial intelligence accelerators are therefore suggested. With fewer test patterns and less test power, the suggested self-test can achieve 100% test accuracy for both delay and stuck-at faults. It is advanced utilizing scan chains made out of functional paths. The hybrid BIST self-test comprises logical BIST to confirm processor unit functionality and memory-BIST to test accumulators, registers, and buffers. Furthermore, the structural and functional properties of the systolic array in the AI accelerator are used to carry out self-diagnosis and self-recovery. Real-time progress is made using the suggested self-test and self-diagnosis, which enables precise fault localization and fault type characterization. Efficient pruning for defective elements of processing with four processing levels is used to advance the suggested self-recovery. It consists of row/column swapping, weight distribution, PE-bypass, and the removal of PE rows/columns with more faults, or, alternatively, recursively employing PE without fault. Both sparse and dense networks can effectively apply the suggested recovery technique. AI accelerators can significantly improve their reliability while barely sacrificing performance. A comprehensive approach with little area overhead is offered by the suggested artificial intelligence assessment and recovery method.

Keywords: Machine learning accelerator, systolic array, built-in self-test, scan chain, fault diagnosis, self recovery.

I. INTRODUCTION

Numerous industries, including signal and image processing, banking, healthcare, automotive, communication, and encryption, have embraced artificial intelligence. [1], [2]. Nevertheless, when a lot of data is involved, the two primary AI operations—multiplication and convolution—take a long time on the software level. As a result, hardware-based solutions—like AI accelerators—have been created [3]. Because the primary operations consist of repeated iterations of basic multiplications and accumulations, it is feasible. Multiple processing components coupled in two dimensions make up the systolic array. Additionally, a multiply-accumulate unit with several registers makes up each PE. Because of this, each PE advances through simple multiplication utilizing weight and input data, and as the calculated data is transferred to the accumulator, each PE's computed data is accumulated. Thus, by employing such hardware-based approach, AI performance may be maximized, as the laborious software problem can be resolved.

However, if permanent errors in the AI accelerator arise, the impacts of such faults may also build during operation as the results of the calculation is gathered. When artificial intelligence (AI) is used in fault-tolerant applications, like neural network models, the cumulative impact of persistent failures may be somewhat tolerated [4, 5, 6]. However, irreversible flaws could have detrimental effects if machine learning boosters are used in industries like aviation and automotive that are closely tied to safety. Furthermore, because to densely integrated PEs, the systolic array is prone to manufacturing flaws [7]. Furthermore, even in cases when the fault velocities of accelerators are modest, the preciseness of an inference reduces dramatically [4], [8]. Reliable AI accelerators must therefore have techniques for detecting and fixing persistent errors. As a result, numerous techniques for identifying and fixing persistent errors have been created. All conventional approaches, however, concentrate on either test or recovery; none have been suggested to help both. Overhead also increases as the self test, diagnosis and recovery are combined into single design.

II. RELATED WORK

Y. Chen, T. Krishna, J. Emer, and V. Sze, (2017) in the paper “EyeRiss: An energy-efficient reconfigurable accelerator for deep convolutional neural networks” offered a method for dissecting a deep neural network accelerator at the cutting edge. By rearranging the design, the accelerator chip and off-chip DRAM for different CNN shapes is optimized. CNNs are a common component of contemporary AI systems, but they also present issues for the underlying hardware in terms of throughput and energy efficiency. This is due to the fact that computing it necessitates a lot of data, which results in a lot of data transportation between the on-and off-chip that uses more energy than processing. Thus, the key to high performance and energy efficiency for any CNN structure is to minimize the energy cost of data transportation. It accomplishes these objectives by utilizing a suggested row stationary processing dataflow on a spatial topology with additional processing features. Moreover, data gating and compression are used to increase energy efficiency.

H. Ma et al., (2019) in the paper “A case study of testing strategy for AI SoC” offered a framework for evaluating the most recent developments in artificial intelligence, which is the engine underlying the industrial revolution and technological revolution that propels social and economic advancement. Several businesses are developing application-specific AI SoCs to speed up the processing of data-intensive AI algorithms. This study describes the experiences with implementing DFT for AI SoC. We employ a high speed Serdes PHY with a lower threshold voltage, which requires a lot of SoC pins, to accomplish higher usage of bandwidth for AI SoC. Because there aren't enough reusable IOs to serve as scan test channels, it negatively affects DFT and ATPG. With ready-to-use silicon bring-up approaches, the solution and trade-offs and pre-silicon verification run time are studied.

A. Chaudhuri, C. Liu, X. Fan, and K. Chakrabarty, (2020) in the paper “C-testing of AI accelerators” offered a way for evaluating Applications using machine learning (AI) predicting use homogeneous designs with identical cores as accelerators. The multiply and accumulate elements, are all present in each core, also known as a processing element (PE). A high CPU time and template count are obtained when uniform array based AI processor chips are tested by executing adaptive test pattern creation at the cluster level. For test development at the PE level, a constant-testable (C-testable) approach is suggested, which ensures that the ATPG effort remains constant as the number of PEs increases. The findings indicate that the suggested approach reduces test pattern count, ATPG duration, and test cycle count for defects in a 128×128 array while maintaining test coverage as compared to the conventional array-level testing. The introduction of customizable scan architecture allows C-testing of the full accelerator array.

U. Solangi, M. Ibtesam, M. Ansari, J. Kim, and S. Park, (2021) in the paper “Test architecture for systolic array of edge-based AI accelerator” A proposed methodology examines the growth of AI processor architectures and their variety of applications, identifying problems with testing duration, test power, performance, and area overhead that call for creative DFT solutions. complete scan DFT is a commercial test approach because to its improved observability and controllability. That might not, however, produce the best test solution given the strict design limitations accelerators. For performance, power, and area (PPA) overhead confined edge-based systolic AI accelerators, a unique test paradigm based on selective-partial scan is explained. Test time and test data volume are decreased when the structural test patterns are partially applied in a functional way, which reduces the testability problem. Additionally, a Launch-on-Capture-based delay fault testing technique is offered for the partial scan-based suggested architecture. Comparing the suggested design to full scan DFT, experimental results demonstrate that it is economical in terms of assessment power and test time.

J. Zhang, T. Gu, K. Basu, and S. Garg, (2018) in the paper “Analyzing and mitigating the impact of permanent faults on a systolic array based neural network accelerator” in which deep neural networks, are being prioritized for hardware acceleration because they offer a framework for assessing their increasing popularity and computational cost. The Google Tensor Processor has embraced a popular topology for DNN acceleration that uses a systolic array based multiplication of matrix unit at its heart. The design of systolic array-based, fault-tolerant DNN acceleration for high number of defects technologies is the subject of this research. With a small loss in classification precision and no run-time efficiency penalty, the TPU can function at fault levels up to 50% because to two innovative strategies: fault-aware construction and fault-aware redesign. Before a TPU chip is deployed, there is a one-time retraining penalty. Optimizations are employed to minimize this one-time penalty to less than 12 minutes.

M. Sadi and U. Guin, (2022) in the paper “Test and yield loss reduction of AI and deep learning accelerators” offered an approach for evaluating data-driven analytics that is starting to gain traction, as demand for specialized machine learning processor chips rises worldwide. Due to their highly packed elements, these accelerators are particularly susceptible to functional failures and manufacturing errors that are typical of advanced semiconductor process nodes, which can result in a large yield loss. By establishing a correlation between the intended accuracy of the desired AI workload and the circuit faults in the accelerator's PEs, an application-driven methodology for binning the AI accelerator chips and yield loss reduction is put forth. In order to construct the current yield loss lowering and test technique, the intrinsic tolerance to faults features of established deep learning models are leveraged along with a selective deactivation strategy of problematic PEs. In order to determine whether the final yield test, an analytical link is derived between the fault location, fault rate, and the correctness of the AI task. For the multiply and aggregate units of the PEs, an ATPG, test flow, and yield loss mitigation aware fault isolation are described. Findings using popular AI/deep learning benchmarks show that the accelerators can withstand 5% fault-rate in PE arrays with less than 1% accuracy loss, allowing these chips to be employed for product-binning and output reduction.

III. SELF TEST AND DIAGNOSIS OF SYSTOLIC ARRAY

Fig. 1 depicts the block diagram of the proposed self test and diagnosis of the systolic array. It consists of test pattern generator, memory elements, address generator, systolic array, comparator and fault processing element diagnosis. The linear feedback shift register is used for generating random test pattern which is used in both memory BIST and logical BIST. Machine learning systolic accelerator consists of series of processing elements connected row and column wise. Each processing element performs multiply and accumulation operation of the weight and activation input data. Fault identification is performed through comparison of the actual output and the expected output of the systolic array. By analyzing the pipelined processing element output of each column the faulty processing elements in the array is identified through fault diagnosis chain.

Fig. 1. Block diagram of self test and diagnosis of systolic array

Fig. 2. Processing element with scan chain. (a) Scan shift processes and (b) scan capture processes.

In order to apply the test data and to obtain the response the processing element in systolic array is modified with scan elements. It helps in achieving the self test process with minimal overhead compared to the conventional design which utilizes more resources. Fig. 2 shows the processing element incorporated with scan elements. Systolic array is an integration of homogeneous processing element in row and column wise to process the weight and activation input. For each processing element, activation input is applied row wise and weight is applied column wise. As shown in Fig. 2a, the processing element uses scan chain S1 for storing and shifting the activation input. Similarly, scan chain S2 is used for storing and shifting weight data. Additional to these two scan elements, the processing element consists of OR gate, multiplexer and scan chain S3 for storing the partial sum. Multiplexer is used to select the data between the current processing element output and the previous processing element output in the same column. Scan_en and PE_disable signals are ORed to produce the selection line of the multiplexer. If Scan_en is '1' the scan shifting of the test data is performed and stored in the corresponding scan elements as shown in Fig. 2a. A 4x4 array requires four clock cycles to place all test data in the processing element. When Scan_en is '0' then partial sum registers S3 captures the multiply and accumulation output of each processing element as shown in Fig. 2b. Scan_en is changed to '1' for next four clock cycles resulting in shift of the captured data for fault identification. All the test data applied to processing elements are similar, resulting in low transition producing minimal shift power.

A. Hybrid BIST

Fig. 3. Flow chart of hybrid BIST.

The hybrid BIST incorporates the memory BIST and logical BIST as shown in Fig. 3. The memory testing is used for testing the memory elements such as registers in PE and accumulators in each column array. The address generator which is in the form of counter generates the address for each memory element and Linear Feedback Shift Register (LFSR) produces the patterns for storing in the register and accumulator. The same address generator is used for reading the stored data in the memory element and their outputs are validated. When the memory test passes then the logical BIST is activated for testing the logical part of the PE. For logical BIST the test pattern generated from LFSR are passes through scan chain and after capturing their results are shifted out. The accumulated output of each column is compared with Multiple Input Signature Register (MISR) for fault identification.

The deterministic pattern can also be applied for testing by storing the data in test memory. LFSR is utilized here because of its low complexity design and to eliminate the use of additional memory. When the comparator indicates the malfunction, fault diagnosis process is activated to identify the faulty one.

B. Self-Diagnosis

The fault output obtained depends on the position of the fault exists. If the multiple and accumulation process is faulty then column scan out data indicates the fault processing element upon comparing with the actual output. If the activation register is faulty then data shifted out from scan chain is compared with the applied data to identify the location. A one bit diagnosis register (DR) is used to identify the fault location through memory ID point each PE. For a 4x4 systolic array 4x4 one bit DR is used. Whenever the comparator shows the difference, then the corresponding DR is enabled else it remains zero. First data comes out from the last row enabling the last row of DR first. At the end of the testing process based on the non-zero elements in DR, the total number of faults and its location in a systolic array is diagnosed. After the identification of fault position the data is used to perform fault recovery.

Fig. 4. Self-diagnosis logic structure

IV. IMPROVED SELF RECOVERY OF SYSTOLIC ARRAY

The proposed self-recovery is progressed using efficient pruning for faulty processing elements with four level of processing. It includes PE-bypass, row/column swapping, weight allocation and eliminating PE row/column with more faults, alternatively using PE without fault recursively. The proposed recovery method can be efficiently used for both sparse and dense networks. The reliability of AI accelerators can drastically increase with negligible performance degradation. The proposed AI testing and recovery provides an integrated solution with a small area overhead as shown in Fig. 4. The improved self recovery method of STRAIT is used for achieving self recovery when all the three possible combinations namely PE_bypass, row/column swapping and weight allocation fails. It eliminates the row or column with more than one fault to be replaced by row or column without any fault in systolic array.

However, when registers in PEs have faults, the effects of the faults propagate to the connected PEs, resulting in column or row faults. It can lead to more severe errors. In this case, disabling only the faulty PE does not resolve the issue. For this reason, a method for disabling all PEs in the row or column where the failure occurs is required. In the case of column faults, it can be a simple solution to disable the corresponding accumulator memories in which the operation results are stored and not to reuse them in the unified buffer. On the other hand, in the case of row faults, they are caused by an activation register problem. For this reason, all PEs in faulty row can be bypassed using PE_disable signal in systolic array.

Fig. 5. Improved self recovery processing order

For example, if row faults exist, disable registers in the corresponding rows where the failure occurs are set to 1 by PE_disable signal, and the entire rows are bypassed. However, it can cause performance degradation because a large number of PEs must be disabled. As shown in Fig. 5a, when the faulty processing element and zero weight coincide then PE_disable is '1' and PE bypass is performed to overcome fault. When the faulty PE and zero weight is in different positions it cannot be recovered using PE bypass, but can be recovered using weight swapping if it falls in same row or column as shown in Fig. 5b. For more than one fault PE weight allocation is used to analyze the possibility of matching zero weight and faulty PE by reordering as shown in Fig. 5c. Therefore, it is preferable to recover faults using weight swapping and weight allocation while minimizing to disable accumulator memories for column skipping and bypass of the entire rows. When weight allocation also fails, the row with more than one error can be eliminated and all the data are transferred from fault row/column to the one which is fault free. For example when 3rd row of 4x4 PE array fails with more than one error as shown in Fig. 5d, then the entire row is eliminated. If the 2nd row doesn't have any fault, then through recursive approach the entire operation of 3rd row is processed by 2nd row to improve the reliability of the AI accelerator. The architecture for this is implemented easily through multiplexer selection between the rows.

V. EVALUATION RESULTS

Fig. 6. Simulation result of processing element in systolic array

Fig. 6 shows the simulation output of PE in systolic array. CLK and RST are the input signals. SCAN_EN is used to select between shift operation (when it is '1') or capture operation (when it is '0'). PE_disable is used to disconnect the processing element from the array when it is found faulty. Each PE is also composed of a multiply-accumulate (MAC) unit with multiple registers. For this reason, each PE progresses simple multiplication using weight(W) and activation data(A), and the calculated data in each PE is accumulated while transferring the calculated data to the accumulator. MUL_OP is the multiplication output and PARTIAL_SUM is the output of the processing element.

Fig. 7. Simulation result of systolic array

Fig. 7. Shows the simulation result of 4x4 systolic array. A1, A2, A3 and A4 is the activation data for four rows and W is the weight for the column. PARTIAL_SUM is the accumulated output of the column containing four processing elements. The systolic array is composed of multiple processing elements (PEs), which are connected in two dimensions. Each PE is also composed of a multiply-accumulate (MAC) unit with multiple registers.

Fig. 8. Simulation result of memory BIST

Fig. 8. shows the simulation result of memory BIST. MODE selection is 0 for memory BIST. LFSR_OP1 and LFSR_OP2 generate the test pattern for weight and activation input data. The memory test using memory BIST (MBIST) is used for testing embedded memories, such as unified buffer and accumulator. LFSR is used to generate the 8-bit and 16-bit test pattern and write/read operation in memory is performed. The comparator out produces the faulty or faultless behavior of the memory elements.

Fig. 9. Simulation result of hybrid BIST and diagnosis without fault

Fig. 10. Simulation result of hybrid BIST and diagnosis with fault

Fig. 9. and Fig. 10. shows the simulation result of hybrid BIST without fault and with fault, respectively. CLK and RST are the input signals. SCAN_EN is used to select between shift operation (when it is '1') or capture operation (when it is '0'). PE_disable is used to disconnect the processing element from the array when it is found faulty. MODE selection is '0' for memory BIST and '1' for logic BIST. INIT1 and INIT2 is the initial seed value of LFSR to generate the test pattern for weight and activation input data. For 4x4 systolic array diagnosis register 4x4 array indicates the '1' when faulty.

Fig. 11. shows the simulation result of improved self recovery. CLK and RST are the input signals. The W is the weight array values in which one in the array indicates weight is present and zero indicates the processing element weight is zero. The DLC array indicates the fault present when it is one or zero when there is no fault in processing element. The improved self recovery method uses reusing of row/column for achieving self recovery when all the three possible combinations namely PE_bypass, row/column swapping and weight allocation fails. X indicates the total number of fault and X1-X4 indicates the faults in each row. X3 is 3 indicating 2 faults in 3rd row, it is eliminated as indicated by ELIMINATE_PE3 as '1'. The row 2 is fault free, so the data to be processed by 3rd row or given to 2nd row recursively through feedback mechanism to improve the self recovery of the AI accelerator.

Fig. 11. Simulation result of improved self recovery with PE Elimination

Table I parameters of self test and diagnosis

ARCHITECTURES	LUT	SLICES	GATE COUNT	POWER (MW)	DELAY (NS)
SELF TEST	349	396	6651	357.88	4.561
PE ARRAY	266	265	5736	354.21	3.650
TOTAL	521	564	10708	377.11	4.589

FAULT TYPE	SA FAULT		TD FAULT	
	STRAIT	STISR	STRAIT	STISR
ARCHITECTURES				
TEST COVERAGE	100%	100%	100%	100%
PATTERN COUNTS	12		18	

Fig. 12. Recovery rate vs sparsity

Table I gives the area, power and delay values of the self test architecture and the systolic array. The self test resource combines the memory BIST and logic BIST utilized to test a 4x4 systolic array. The overall design occupies 521 LUTs and 564 slices along with 377.11mW power consumption and 4.589ns of critical path delay when synthesized using Xilinx FPGA targeting Virtex-4 family. Fig. 12 shows the graphical analysis between recovery rate and sparsity for four categories of recovery mechanism. PE elimination and recursive approach can achieve 100% recovery with minimal sparsity with 10% in the systolic array.

Fig. 13. Output of FPGA KIT

VI. CONCLUSION

The design for self test, diagnosis and higher recovery for a systolic array-based AI accelerator is proposed. It provides efficient comprehensive solution to identify the fault in memory and logical element. The processing element is modified to enhance the testing capability with minimum area overhead. The scan design incorporated to the processing element identifies the fault without need of large number of test pattern. The diagnosis method using diagnosis register helps in locating the fault elements. Fault recovery is improved in the processed mechanism through a four step process. It includes PE-bypass, row/column swapping, weight allocation and eliminating PE row/column with more faults, alternatively using PE without fault recursively. The proposed recovery method can be efficiently used for both sparse and dense networks. 100% fault recovery is achieved for a minimally sparse systolic array. Therefore, the proposed AI accelerator can contribute to securing the reliability of mission-critical applications by supporting self-test, self-diagnosis, and self-recovery features.

VII. REFERENCES

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